

Floor mapping - a tool for precise positioning and enhanced safety in modern smart spaces

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1. Smart spaces

Smart homes, smart offices, and other smart spaces are becoming increasingly common. Modern buildings and spaces are equipped with numerous smart devices and furniture that not only improve the standard of living, automate processes and increase the energy efficiency of the building, but also monitor daily activities, assist the elderly and protect health and even life. Smart spaces are a great convenience for the infirm and disabled, improving comfort and reducing the risk of dangerous situations (monitoring parameters such as carbon monoxide and dioxide, smoke or electrical short circuits). The smart approach is not limited only to technology (electronic devices) but also to designing spaces with people's comfort, health, well-being and safety in mind.

In hospitals and nursing homes, smart solutions support the care of people with disabilities, the elderly, and those with dementia [1], [2]. Properly designed spaces can not only increase safety, but also improve the well-being of patients and residents, support their independence and reduce the stress associated with changing their environment.

New buildings designed in the smart trend are constructed with a specific purpose in mind for their intended use. However, existing buildings or spaces can be modernised to at least partially meet the requirements of smart spaces. However, often limited funds for construction or modernisation do not allow spaces to be equipped with the latest smart technologies.

In smart spaces, the aim is to create environments that are more responsive, sustainable and fitted to the individual needs of users. Smart technologies (e.g. various types of sensors or devices) are constantly developing, integrating with everyday life and providing increasingly advanced functions. It is worth noting that the development of smart spaces is not limited to the interiors of buildings. It is also increasingly including urban spaces, parks, and other public places, which, thanks to the use of IoT (internet of things) devices, are becoming more friendly, accessible and safe for all residents.

2. Safety first

Wearable technology and intelligent systems are continually enhancing the safety and quality of life for the elderly and individuals with disabilities. Sensors that monitor health parameters, such as heart rate, blood pressure, and activity levels, enable a rapid response to disturbing changes in health. For example, wearable devices can detect irregularities in heart rhythm, falls or gait problems, alerting the user or caregiver to potential danger [3], [4]. In many cases, such a rapid response can prevent serious health consequences.

Additionally, systems that monitor user activity are a significant innovation for the elderly or those with disabilities, who are often at risk of injuries due to instability or limited mobility. Smart sensors can not only immediately notify family or medical services about such an event but also analyse data to predict the risk of further falls. Thanks to this, appropriate preventive actions can be implemented, such as physiotherapy or adapting the environment to the needs of the elderly person.

Additionally, real-time location systems are being increasingly used to track the positions of the elderly or those with disabilities, particularly those with memory disorders such as

dementia. These systems can help caregivers quickly locate a lost person or notify when leaving a safe zone.

Data collected from multiple sensors is used by various types of algorithms or artificial intelligence for analysis and interpretation [5], [6]. Machine learning algorithms can recognise patterns of behaviour and habits that may indicate deteriorating health, such as reduced physical activity, a change in the way people walk or fall detection [7]. Thanks to this, caregivers, doctors, and users themselves can respond to potential problems more quickly, thereby increasing the chances of implementing effective preventive measures.

These innovations, based on smart technologies and wearable sensors, aim to create a more supportive and safer environment for the elderly and individuals with disabilities, while enhancing their independence and quality of life. In this way, these technologies become an invaluable tool in healthcare, changing the way we care for the most vulnerable groups in society.

3. Positioning

Various technologies can be used to determine the position, providing additional information to the analysis systems. The appropriate choice may be dictated by the target environment, range, or frequency of receiving position information. Systems are often combined to eliminate the weaknesses of individual systems. For indoor navigation, systems based on technologies such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, UWB (ultra-wideband), IMU (inertial measurement unit), RFID (radio frequency identification), LiDAR (light detection and ranging), or camera vision systems are commonly used. The same technologies are used to position people, animals, vehicles and other objects.

RFID technology is effectively used in homes to track elderly individuals. The data gathered allows for analysis of their movement patterns, trajectories, and the amount of exercise performed by the elderly people [8]. Camera vision systems are utilised to localise people and detect falls, particularly through the use of infrared cameras to protect people's privacy [9]. Bluetooth is used not only to locate people but also to track medical equipment, which is crucial for patient diagnosis and treatment [10]. UWB allows for determining the position with an accuracy of several centimetres. This technology is used in smart healthcare due to its secure communication and energy efficiency [11].

To increase the prediction accuracy of warning systems or user assistance systems, it is beneficial to know the environment in which people require assistance with mobility - knowing the space in which the elderly, disabled, or visually impaired move and their position will allow for sending appropriate messages about obstacles they may encounter on their way, or even guiding a blind person to their destination.

4. Floor mapping

Objects such as chairs, cabinets, or other people can be detected using camera vision systems, which can accurately identify both static and dynamic objects in the scene and classify them successfully. A bigger problem is the unevenness of the ground on which people move. An uneven surface or a floor drop can lead to a trip and then a fall, which can have catastrophic consequences, especially for the elderly. Additionally, data from wearable sensors can falsely detect gait problems that are not due to deteriorating health, but rather to an uneven floor. Additionally, information about the floor's condition and potential obstacles is crucial for warning systems that can identify hazardous areas.

Information about the condition of the floor can be used during the modernisation of a building for specialised purposes (e.g., nursing homes) to take appropriate remedial steps. In turn, in new or modernised buildings, it can provide information about places with an increased risk of falling.

Specialised laser scanners can be used to map the floor, which can accurately reflect the surface of scanned objects or rooms. Laser scanning is time-consuming and expensive, and data analysis is often complex, requiring a significant amount of time and resources [12], [13].

Floor scanning can be automated using an AGV (automated guided vehicle) that moves around the room and collects data about the surface (floor). A suitably placed LiDAR can be used to scan the surface itself, based on which the type of surface, its textures, and quality can be determined [14]. However, with this type of scanning, there is no reference, or its determination is complex and burdened with a significant error regarding the slope of the floor on the scale of the entire room or building, because scanning is performed in relation to the position and orientation of the AGV.

A prototype of an AGV equipped with a measuring probe and auto-levelling was built to enable floor mapping and level determination (Fig. 1). The AGV can either map the floor of a room manually or automatically in relation to a reference level. The construction of the prototype, carried out at the Silesian University of Technology, involved people from various fields, including computer science, electronics, and geodesy.

Fig. 1. The AGV for floor mapping with an auto-levelling system

The AGV for floor mapping is equipped with a variety of devices and sensors for surrounding perception, positioning and mapping the levelness of the floor and its surface. The vehicle utilises an Arduino Due for control and a Raspberry Pi for wireless communication and localisation. The vehicle's position in the room is determined using a 2D LiDAR and a SLAM (simultaneous localisation and mapping) algorithm. Using point clouds from LiDAR, encoder readings mounted on wheel motors, and IMU (inertial measurement unit) data, the AGV can accurately create a map of the room while simultaneously localising itself [15]. The precise location of the AGV is essential for accurately correlating measurements with the room layout.

Floor sampling is conducted using a measuring probe that moves vertically along a rail [16]. During the downward movement, a switch detects the floor level. Then, as the probe moves upward, the steps of the stepper motor are counted until it reaches a laser beam, which is detected by light-dependent resistors (LDRs). The distance between the reference level (defined by the laser beam) and the floor is calculated based on the number of steps taken by the stepper motor that drives the measuring probe. The measured distance, along with the position information, is then sent to the database.

The AGV is equipped with a self-levelling system to ensure that measurements are taken at a specific chosen location. Levelling the AGV facilitates the detection of the laser beam and minimises additional transformations of the position and the obtained measurement. The levelling system utilises data from the IMU and 3 extendable legs (Fig. 2). After reaching the target measurement position, the levelling system extends the legs and levels the AGV. Then the measuring probe measures the distance. After the floor sampling, the probe returns to the standby position, and the supports retract.

Fig. 2. The AGV auto-levelling system

AGV is equipped with a mobile application that allows to present the measurements using a heatmap (Fig. 3). Based on the measurements, it is possible to determine the condition of the floor, identify its inclination (Fig. 3. (a)) and detect objects on it, such as a carpet (Fig. 3. (b)).

Fig. 3. The floor visualisation in the mobile application

Conclusion

The developed AGV prototype for floor mapping serves as an affordable alternative to expensive and time-consuming laser scanning methods. The presented AGV can measure the levelness of a room's surface, allowing for the identification of areas with an increased risk of falling. Additionally, integrating the mapped floor data with information from wearable sensors can enhance the accuracy of algorithms designed to detect gait instability.

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